

On the Deduction of Covalent Bonds and Rings Equations for Cyclic π -Systems

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Abstract: This study presents novel deduction methods for equations that are similar to the degree of unsaturation (DoU), which can be used to calculate the number of bonds and rings for specific cases of cyclic unsaturated organic molecules. In previous work, we have published several papers that contain both simpler versions and the same mathematical relationships presented here. However, those studies focused primarily on their application to a wide range of molecules, supported by detailed examples, rather than on their derivation. Additionally, this study discusses the limitations of these equations, explores potential use cases, and compares our approach with those previously reported in the literature.

Keywords: Deduction methods, Organic molecules, Equations, Covalent bonds, Rings

1. Introduction

In any area of science that deals with mathematical relationships [1], it is important to demonstrate how those relationships are derived in order to make them more credible and understandable to readers. Therefore, in this manuscript we aim to explain in detail the equations we previously published [2-4], as well as new ones that can be derived using the same approach, so that readers can replicate the process and identify similar equations by modifying the initial conditions or the types of molecules. Starting from the well-known degree of unsaturation and Euler's formula for polyhedra [5-6], applied to molecular structures that are based on covalent bond theory, and following the logic of simpler formulas [7,2] alongside their more complex counterparts [3,4], we have constructed a step-by-step derivation process that leads to generalized equations for cyclic unsaturated molecules, based on the number of atoms, their valences, and the percentages of bonds and rings. However, these equations have limitations, including a mathematical overlap which arises from the initial assumptions regarding bond and ring types. Overall, they represent a step forward in the application of mathematics to the classical representation of molecules for the calculation of various numerical variables.

2. Materials and Methods

As an introduction to the following deduction methods presented in the next section, we first define each variable and formula used to derive the main equations:

- the number of sigma bonds in a molecule (n_{σ})
- the number of pi bonds in a molecule (n_{π})
- the number of rings in a molecule (n_r)
- the number of single bonds in a molecule (n_s)

- the number of double bonds in a molecule (n_d)
- the number of triple bonds in a molecule (n_t)
- the number of chemical elements in a molecule (i)
- the number of atoms that correspond to a chemical element (n_i)
- the valence of a chemical element (v_i)
- the percentage of pi bonds in a molecule (p_π)
- the percentage of rings in a molecule (p_r)
- the percentage of double bonds in a molecule (p_d)
- the percentage of triple bonds in a molecule (p_t)

The initial formulas from which we started our reasoning can be divided into four categories. The first three are common and well known, while the fourth category is based on our latest publication which introduces a new chemical „concept” named total unsaturation (TU) [4]. Total unsaturation can be more accurately described as a mathematical relationship established between chemical variables.

$$A) \text{ DoU} = 1 + \frac{1}{2}(\sum_i n_i(v_i - 2)) ; n_\pi + n_r = 1 + \frac{1}{2}(\sum_i n_i(v_i - 2))$$

$$B) n_d + 2n_t = n_\pi ; n_\sigma = n_i + n_r - 1$$

$$C) n_s = n_i + n_r - n_t - 1 ; n_s = n_i + n_r - n_d - 1 ; n_s = n_i + n_r - n_d - n_t - 1$$

$$D) p_\pi + p_r = \text{TU} ; p_\pi + p_r = 100\%$$

Additionally there will be six cases presented in the results and discussion section that consist of inequalities established between the percentage of bonds and rings.

- 1) Cyclic unsaturated organic compounds with double bonds in which:
 $p_\pi > p_r ; p_d > p_r ; p_t = 0$
- 2) Cyclic unsaturated organic compounds with triple bonds in which:
 $p_\pi > p_r ; p_t > p_r ; p_d = 0$
- 3) Cyclic unsaturated organic compounds with double bonds in which:
 $p_\pi < p_r ; p_d < p_r ; p_t = 0$
- 4) Cyclic unsaturated organic compounds with triple bonds in which:
 $p_\pi < p_r ; p_t < p_r ; p_d = 0$
- 5) Cyclic unsaturated organic compounds with double and triple bonds in which:
 $p_\pi > p_r ; p_d + p_t > p_r ; p_d = p_t$
- 6) Cyclic unsaturated organic compounds with double and triple bonds in which:
 $p_\pi < p_r ; p_d + p_t < p_r ; p_d = p_t$

3. Results and Discussion

Practically speaking, the scope of the following equations is to connect variables used for molecular recognition in spectroscopy [8] and spectrometry techniques [9]. The main difference between our formulas and existing ones is that we propose substituting variables that are difficult to determine experimentally in unknown molecular structures, such as the exact number of bonds and rings, with simpler variables. These include the number of atoms, their valences, and multiple percentage-based assumptions. In principle, this could help infer more complex structural features of molecules from simpler measurable quantities, within the framework of valence bond theory [10,11], and without using molecular orbital theory [12]. However, at present these equations are not yet practically applicable and should be regarded just as a theoretical novelty and curiosity [13], due to a major unresolved limitation [14]. Specifically, the mathematical overlap that arises when calculating chemical variables across multiple cases proves to be unavoidable. Although not explicitly stated, this issue can be observed in our previous work [2-4] by swapping the number of bonds and rings in the examples, particularly when these quantities are not known in advance, as would be the case in practical applications.

3.1. Cyclic unsaturated organic compounds with double bonds in which $p_{\pi} > p_r$; $p_d > p_r$; $p_t = 0$

We begin the deduction process under the following assumptions:

$$n_{\pi} + n_r = 1 + \frac{1}{2}(\sum_i n_i(v_i - 2)) \text{ where } x = \frac{n_{\pi}}{n_r} \text{ and } x > 1.$$

$$3.1.1. \quad n_{\pi} + n_r = 1 + \frac{1}{2}(\sum_i n_i(v_i - 2))$$

$$xn_r + n_r = 1 + \frac{1}{2}(\sum_i n_i(v_i - 2))$$

$$n_r \cdot (x + 1) = 1 + \frac{1}{2}(\sum_i n_i(v_i - 2))$$

$$n_r = \frac{1 + \frac{1}{2}(\sum_i n_i(v_i - 2))}{x + 1} \Rightarrow n_r = \frac{2 + \sum_i n_i(v_i - 2)}{2x + 2}$$

The ratio $\frac{n_{\pi}}{n_r}$ can be written as $\frac{p_{\pi}}{p_r}$ in order to generalize for all possible cyclic unsaturated molecular systems which adhere to the previously stated conditions.

$$n_r = \frac{2 + \sum_i n_i(v_i - 2)}{2\left(\frac{n_{\pi}}{n_r}\right) + 2} \Rightarrow n_r = \frac{2 + \sum_i n_i(v_i - 2)}{2\left(\frac{p_{\pi}}{p_r}\right) + 2} ; n_r = \frac{2 + \sum_i n_i(v_i - 2)}{4 + 2\left(\frac{p_{\pi}}{p_r} - 1\right)} \quad (1)$$

Now to deduce the equations for n_{π} , n_{σ} , n_s we will substitute multiple times different variables in the starting formulas.

$$3.1.2. \quad n_{\pi} + n_r = 1 + \frac{1}{2} (\sum_i n_i (v_i - 2))$$

$$n_{\pi} + \frac{2 + \sum_i n_i (v_i - 2)}{4 + 2 \left(\frac{p_{\pi}}{p_r} - 1 \right)} = 1 + \frac{1}{2} (\sum_i n_i (v_i - 2))$$

$$n_{\pi} = 1 + \frac{1}{2} (\sum_i n_i (v_i - 2)) - \frac{2 + \sum_i n_i (v_i - 2)}{4 + 2 \left(\frac{p_{\pi}}{p_r} - 1 \right)}$$

$$n_{\pi} = \frac{4 + 2 \left(\frac{p_{\pi}}{p_r} - 1 \right) + (2 + \left(\frac{p_{\pi}}{p_r} - 1 \right)) (\sum_i n_i (v_i - 2)) - (2 + \sum_i n_i (v_i - 2))}{4 + 2 \left(\frac{p_{\pi}}{p_r} - 1 \right)}$$

$$n_{\pi} = \frac{\sum_i n_i (v_i - 2) + \left(\frac{p_{\pi}}{p_r} - 1 \right) (\sum_i n_i (v_i - 2) + 2) + 2}{4 + 2 \left(\frac{p_{\pi}}{p_r} - 1 \right)} \quad (2)$$

Also, because of the initial conditions the following equality occurs:

$$n_{\pi} = n_d = \frac{\sum_i n_i (v_i - 2) + \left(\frac{p_{\pi}}{p_r} - 1 \right) (\sum_i n_i (v_i - 2) + 2) + 2}{4 + 2 \left(\frac{p_{\pi}}{p_r} - 1 \right)} \quad (3)$$

$$3.1.3. \quad n_{\sigma} = n_i + n_r - 1$$

$$n_{\sigma} = n_i + \frac{2 + \sum_i n_i (v_i - 2)}{4 + 2 \left(\frac{p_{\pi}}{p_r} - 1 \right)} - 1$$

$$n_{\sigma} = \frac{n_i (4 + 2 \left(\frac{p_{\pi}}{p_r} - 1 \right)) + 2 + \sum_i n_i (v_i - 2) - 4 - 2 \left(\frac{p_{\pi}}{p_r} - 1 \right)}{4 + 2 \left(\frac{p_{\pi}}{p_r} - 1 \right)}$$

$$n_{\sigma} = \frac{\sum_i n_i (v_i + 2) + 2 \left(\frac{p_{\pi}}{p_r} - 1 \right) (n_i - 1) - 2}{4 + 2 \left(\frac{p_{\pi}}{p_r} - 1 \right)} \quad (4)$$

$$3.1.4. \quad n_s = n_i + n_r - n_d - 1$$

$$n_s = n_i + \frac{2 + \sum_i n_i (v_i - 2)}{4 + 2 \left(\frac{p_{\pi}}{p_r} - 1 \right)} - \frac{\sum_i n_i (v_i - 2) + \left(\frac{p_{\pi}}{p_r} - 1 \right) (\sum_i n_i (v_i - 2) + 2) + 2}{4 + 2 \left(\frac{p_{\pi}}{p_r} - 1 \right)} - 1$$

$$n_s = \frac{n_i (4 + 2 \left(\frac{p_{\pi}}{p_r} - 1 \right)) - \left(\frac{p_{\pi}}{p_r} - 1 \right) (\sum_i n_i (v_i - 2) + 2) - 4 - 2 \left(\frac{p_{\pi}}{p_r} - 1 \right)}{4 + 2 \left(\frac{p_{\pi}}{p_r} - 1 \right)}$$

$$n_s = \frac{4(n_i - 1) - \left(\frac{p_{\pi}}{p_r} - 1 \right) (\sum_i n_i (v_i - 4) + 4)}{4 + 2 \left(\frac{p_{\pi}}{p_r} - 1 \right)} \quad (5)$$

3.2. Cyclic unsaturated organic compounds with triple bonds in which $p_\pi > p_r$; $p_t > p_r$; $p_d = 0$

In this case, the equations for n_r , n_π , n_σ can be deduced exactly the same as the previous ones, however there are new deductions for n_t and n_s .

$$n_\pi + n_r = 1 + \frac{1}{2} (\sum_i n_i (v_i - 2)) \text{ where } x = \frac{n_\pi}{n_r} \text{ and } x > 1.$$

3.2.1.

$$n_r = \frac{2 + \sum_i n_i (v_i - 2)}{4 + 2 \left(\frac{p_\pi}{p_r} - 1 \right)} \quad (1)$$

3.2.2.

$$n_\pi = \frac{\sum_i n_i (v_i - 2) + \left(\frac{p_\pi}{p_r} - 1 \right) (\sum_i n_i (v_i - 2) + 2) + 2}{4 + 2 \left(\frac{p_\pi}{p_r} - 1 \right)} \quad (2)$$

Because of the initial conditions, the number of triple bonds is half the number of π -bonds:

$$n_t = \frac{\sum_i n_i (v_i - 2) + \left(\frac{p_\pi}{p_r} - 1 \right) (\sum_i n_i (v_i - 2) + 2) + 2}{8 + 4 \left(\frac{p_\pi}{p_r} - 1 \right)} \quad (6)$$

3.2.3.

$$n_\sigma = \frac{\sum_i n_i (v_i + 2) + 2 \left(\frac{p_\pi}{p_r} - 1 \right) (n_i - 1) - 2}{4 + 2 \left(\frac{p_\pi}{p_r} - 1 \right)} \quad (4)$$

3.2.4. $n_s = n_i + n_r - n_t - 1$

$$n_s = n_i + \frac{2 + \sum_i n_i (v_i - 2)}{4 + 2 \left(\frac{p_\pi}{p_r} - 1 \right)} - \frac{\sum_i n_i (v_i - 2) + \left(\frac{p_\pi}{p_r} - 1 \right) (\sum_i n_i (v_i - 2) + 2) + 2}{8 + 4 \left(\frac{p_\pi}{p_r} - 1 \right)} - 1$$

$$n_s = \frac{n_i (8 + 4 \left(\frac{p_\pi}{p_r} - 1 \right)) + \sum_i n_i (v_i - 2) + \left(\frac{p_\pi}{p_r} - 1 \right) (\sum_i n_i (v_i - 2) + 2) - 6 - 4 \left(\frac{p_\pi}{p_r} - 1 \right)}{8 + 4 \left(\frac{p_\pi}{p_r} - 1 \right)}$$

$$n_s = \frac{\sum_i n_i (v_i + 6) + \left(\frac{p_\pi}{p_r} - 1 \right) (\sum_i n_i (6 - v_i) - 6) - 6}{8 + 4 \left(\frac{p_\pi}{p_r} - 1 \right)} \quad (7)$$

3.3. Cyclic unsaturated organic compounds with double bonds in which $p_{\pi} < p_r$; $p_d < p_r$; $p_t = 0$

We begin the deduction process under the following assumptions:

$$n_{\pi} + n_r = 1 + \frac{1}{2}(\sum_i n_i(v_i - 2)) \text{ where } y = \frac{n_r}{n_{\pi}} \text{ and } y > 1.$$

$$3.3.1. \quad n_{\pi} + n_r = 1 + \frac{1}{2}(\sum_i n_i(v_i - 2))$$

$$n_{\pi} + yn_{\pi} = 1 + \frac{1}{2}(\sum_i n_i(v_i - 2))$$

$$n_{\pi} \cdot (1 + y) = 1 + \frac{1}{2}(\sum_i n_i(v_i - 2))$$

$$n_{\pi} = \frac{1 + \frac{1}{2}(\sum_i n_i(v_i - 2))}{1 + y} \Rightarrow n_{\pi} = \frac{2 + \sum_i n_i(v_i - 2)}{2 + 2y}$$

The ratio $\frac{n_r}{n_{\pi}}$ can be written as $\frac{p_r}{p_{\pi}}$ in order to generalize for all possible cyclic unsaturated molecular systems which adhere to the previously stated conditions.

$$n_{\pi} = \frac{2 + \sum_i n_i(v_i - 2)}{2 + 2\left(\frac{n_r}{n_{\pi}}\right)} \Rightarrow n_{\pi} = \frac{2 + \sum_i n_i(v_i - 2)}{2 + 2\left(\frac{p_r}{p_{\pi}}\right)} ; \quad n_{\pi} = \frac{2 + \sum_i n_i(v_i - 2)}{4 + 2\left(\frac{p_r}{p_{\pi}} - 1\right)} \quad (8)$$

Now to deduce the equations for n_r , n_{σ} , n_s we will substitute multiple times different variables in the starting formulas.

Also, because of the initial conditions the following equality occurs:

$$n_{\pi} = n_d = \frac{2 + \sum_i n_i(v_i - 2)}{4 + 2\left(\frac{p_r}{p_{\pi}} - 1\right)} \quad (9)$$

$$3.3.2. \quad n_{\pi} + n_r = 1 + \frac{1}{2}(\sum_i n_i(v_i - 2))$$

$$\frac{2 + \sum_i n_i(v_i - 2)}{4 + 2\left(\frac{p_r}{p_{\pi}} - 1\right)} + n_r = 1 + \frac{1}{2}(\sum_i n_i(v_i - 2))$$

$$n_r = 1 + \frac{1}{2}(\sum_i n_i(v_i - 2)) - \frac{2 + \sum_i n_i(v_i - 2)}{4 + 2\left(\frac{p_r}{p_{\pi}} - 1\right)}$$

$$n_r = \frac{4 + 2\left(\frac{p_r}{p_{\pi}} - 1\right) + (2 + \left(\frac{p_r}{p_{\pi}} - 1\right))(\sum_i n_i(v_i - 2)) - (2 + \sum_i n_i(v_i - 2))}{4 + 2\left(\frac{p_r}{p_{\pi}} - 1\right)}$$

$$n_r = \frac{\sum_i n_i (v_i - 2) + \left(\frac{p_r}{p_\pi} - 1\right) (\sum_i n_i (v_i - 2) + 2) + 2}{4 + 2\left(\frac{p_r}{p_\pi} - 1\right)} \quad (10)$$

3.3.3. $n_\sigma = n_i + n_r - 1$

$$n_\sigma = n_i + \frac{\sum_i n_i (v_i - 2) + \left(\frac{p_r}{p_\pi} - 1\right) (\sum_i n_i (v_i - 2) + 2) + 2}{4 + 2\left(\frac{p_r}{p_\pi} - 1\right)} - 1$$

$$n_\sigma = \frac{n_i (4 + 2\left(\frac{p_r}{p_\pi} - 1\right)) + \sum_i n_i (v_i - 2) + \left(\frac{p_r}{p_\pi} - 1\right) (\sum_i n_i (v_i - 2) + 2) - 2 - 2\left(\frac{p_r}{p_\pi} - 1\right)}{4 + 2\left(\frac{p_r}{p_\pi} - 1\right)}$$

$$n_\sigma = \frac{\sum_i n_i (v_i + 2) + \left(\frac{p_r}{p_\pi} - 1\right) \sum_i n_i v_i - 2}{4 + 2\left(\frac{p_r}{p_\pi} - 1\right)} \quad (11)$$

3.3.4. $n_s = n_i + n_r - n_d - 1$

$$n_s = n_i + \frac{\sum_i n_i (v_i - 2) + \left(\frac{p_r}{p_\pi} - 1\right) (\sum_i n_i (v_i - 2) + 2) + 2}{4 + 2\left(\frac{p_r}{p_\pi} - 1\right)} - \frac{2 + \sum_i n_i (v_i - 2)}{4 + 2\left(\frac{p_r}{p_\pi} - 1\right)} - 1$$

$$n_s = \frac{n_i (4 + 2\left(\frac{p_r}{p_\pi} - 1\right)) + \left(\frac{p_r}{p_\pi} - 1\right) (\sum_i n_i (v_i - 2) + 2) - 4 - 2\left(\frac{p_r}{p_\pi} - 1\right)}{4 + 2\left(\frac{p_r}{p_\pi} - 1\right)}$$

$$n_s = \frac{4(n_i - 1) + \left(\frac{p_r}{p_\pi} - 1\right) \sum_i n_i v_i}{4 + 2\left(\frac{p_r}{p_\pi} - 1\right)} \quad (12)$$

3.4. Cyclic unsaturated organic compounds with triple bonds in which

$$p_\pi < p_r ; p_t < p_r ; p_d = 0$$

In this case, the equations for n_π , n_r , n_σ can be deduced exactly the same as the previous ones, however there are new deductions for n_t and n_s .

$$n_\pi + n_r = 1 + \frac{1}{2} (\sum_i n_i (v_i - 2)) \text{ where } y = \frac{n_r}{n_\pi} \text{ and } y > 1.$$

3.4.1.

$$n_\pi = \frac{2 + \sum_i n_i (v_i - 2)}{4 + 2\left(\frac{p_r}{p_\pi} - 1\right)} \quad (8)$$

Because of the initial conditions, the number of triple bonds is half the number of π -bonds:

$$n_t = \frac{2 + \sum_i n_i (v_i - 2)}{8 + 4\left(\frac{p_r}{p_\pi} - 1\right)} \quad (13)$$

3.4.2.

$$n_r = \frac{\sum_i n_i (v_i - 2) + \left(\frac{p_r}{p_\pi} - 1\right) (\sum_i n_i (v_i - 2) + 2) + 2}{4 + 2\left(\frac{p_r}{p_\pi} - 1\right)} \quad (10)$$

3.4.3.

$$n_\sigma = \frac{\sum_i n_i (v_i + 2) + \left(\frac{p_r}{p_\pi} - 1\right) \sum_i n_i v_i - 2}{4 + 2\left(\frac{p_r}{p_\pi} - 1\right)} \quad (11)$$

$$3.4.4. \quad n_s = n_i + n_r - n_t - 1$$

$$n_s = n_i + \frac{\sum_i n_i (v_i - 2) + \left(\frac{p_r}{p_\pi} - 1\right) (\sum_i n_i (v_i - 2) + 2) + 2}{4 + 2\left(\frac{p_r}{p_\pi} - 1\right)} - \frac{2 + \sum_i n_i (v_i - 2)}{8 + 4\left(\frac{p_r}{p_\pi} - 1\right)} - 1$$

$$n_s = \frac{n_i (8 + 4\left(\frac{p_r}{p_\pi} - 1\right)) + \sum_i n_i (v_i - 2) + 2\left(\frac{p_r}{p_\pi} - 1\right) (\sum_i n_i (v_i - 2) + 2) - 6 - 4\left(\frac{p_r}{p_\pi} - 1\right)}{8 + 4\left(\frac{p_r}{p_\pi} - 1\right)}$$

$$n_s = \frac{\sum_i n_i (v_i + 6) + 2\left(\frac{p_r}{p_\pi} - 1\right) \sum_i n_i v_i - 6}{8 + 4\left(\frac{p_r}{p_\pi} - 1\right)} \quad (14)$$

3.5. Cyclic unsaturated organic compounds with double and triple bonds in which

$$p_\pi > p_r ; p_d + p_t > p_r ; p_d = p_t$$

The equations for n_r , n_π , n_σ are the same as the ones from the subchapter 3.1. However, there are new deductions that lead to novel equations for n_d , n_t , n_s .

3.5.1.

$$n_r = \frac{2 + \sum_i n_i (v_i - 2)}{4 + 2\left(\frac{p_\pi}{p_r} - 1\right)} \quad (1)$$

3.5.2.

$$n_{\pi} = \frac{\sum_i n_i(v_i-2) + \left(\frac{p_{\pi}}{p_r} - 1\right)(\sum_i n_i(v_i-2) + 2) + 2}{4 + 2\left(\frac{p_{\pi}}{p_r} - 1\right)} \quad (2)$$

3.5.3.

$$n_{\sigma} = \frac{\sum_i n_i(v_i+2) + 2\left(\frac{p_{\pi}}{p_r} - 1\right)(n_i-1) - 2}{4 + 2\left(\frac{p_{\pi}}{p_r} - 1\right)} \quad (4)$$

3.5.4.

We begin the deduction process under the following assumptions:

$$n_d + 2n_t = n_{\pi} \quad \text{and} \quad n_d = n_t$$

$$n_d + 2n_t = \frac{\sum_i n_i(v_i-2) + \left(\frac{p_{\pi}}{p_r} - 1\right)(\sum_i n_i(v_i-2) + 2) + 2}{4 + 2\left(\frac{p_{\pi}}{p_r} - 1\right)}$$

$$n_d = \frac{\sum_i n_i(v_i-2) + \left(\frac{p_{\pi}}{p_r} - 1\right)(\sum_i n_i(v_i-2) + 2) + 2}{12 + 6\left(\frac{p_{\pi}}{p_r} - 1\right)} \quad (15)$$

3.5.5.

Because $n_d = n_t$ the number of triple bonds is:

$$n_t = \frac{\sum_i n_i(v_i-2) + \left(\frac{p_{\pi}}{p_r} - 1\right)(\sum_i n_i(v_i-2) + 2) + 2}{12 + 6\left(\frac{p_{\pi}}{p_r} - 1\right)} \quad (16)$$

3.5.6.

$$n_s = n_i + n_r - n_d - n_t - 1$$

$$n_s = n_i + \frac{2 + \sum_i n_i(v_i-2)}{4 + 2\left(\frac{p_{\pi}}{p_r} - 1\right)} - \frac{\sum_i n_i(v_i-2) + \left(\frac{p_{\pi}}{p_r} - 1\right)(\sum_i n_i(v_i-2) + 2) + 2}{6 + 3\left(\frac{p_{\pi}}{p_r} - 1\right)} - 1$$

$$n_s = \frac{n_i(12 + 6\left(\frac{p_{\pi}}{p_r} - 1\right)) + \sum_i n_i(v_i-2) - 2\left(\frac{p_{\pi}}{p_r} - 1\right)(\sum_i n_i(v_i-2) + 2) - 10 - 6\left(\frac{p_{\pi}}{p_r} - 1\right)}{12 + 6\left(\frac{p_{\pi}}{p_r} - 1\right)}$$

$$n_s = \frac{\sum_i n_i(v_i+10) + \left(\frac{p_{\pi}}{p_r} - 1\right)(\sum_i n_i(10 - 2v_i) - 10) - 10}{12 + 6\left(\frac{p_{\pi}}{p_r} - 1\right)} \quad (17)$$

3.6. Cyclic unsaturated organic compounds with double and triple bonds in which

$$p_{\pi} < p_r ; p_d + p_t < p_r ; p_d = p_t$$

The equations for n_{π} , n_r , n_{σ} are the same as the ones from the subchapter 3.3. However, there are new deductions that lead to novel equations for n_d , n_t , n_s .

3.6.1.

$$n_{\pi} = \frac{2 + \sum_i n_i (v_i - 2)}{4 + 2\left(\frac{p_r}{p_{\pi}} - 1\right)} \quad (8)$$

3.6.2.

$$n_r = \frac{\sum_i n_i (v_i - 2) + \left(\frac{p_r}{p_{\pi}} - 1\right) (\sum_i n_i (v_i - 2) + 2) + 2}{4 + 2\left(\frac{p_r}{p_{\pi}} - 1\right)} \quad (10)$$

3.6.3.

$$n_{\sigma} = \frac{\sum_i n_i (v_i + 2) + \left(\frac{p_r}{p_{\pi}} - 1\right) \sum_i n_i v_i - 2}{4 + 2\left(\frac{p_r}{p_{\pi}} - 1\right)} \quad (11)$$

3.6.4.

We begin the deduction process under the following assumptions:

$$n_d + 2n_t = n_{\pi} \quad \text{and} \quad n_d = n_t$$

$$n_d + 2n_t = \frac{2 + \sum_i n_i (v_i - 2)}{4 + 2\left(\frac{p_r}{p_{\pi}} - 1\right)}$$

$$n_d = \frac{2 + \sum_i n_i (v_i - 2)}{12 + 6\left(\frac{p_r}{p_{\pi}} - 1\right)} \quad (18)$$

3.6.5.

Because $n_d = n_t$ the number of triple bonds is:

$$n_t = \frac{2 + \sum_i n_i (v_i - 2)}{12 + 6\left(\frac{p_r}{p_{\pi}} - 1\right)} \quad (19)$$

3.6.6.

$$n_s = n_i + n_r - n_d - n_t - 1$$

$$n_s = n_i + \frac{\sum_i n_i (v_i - 2) + \left(\frac{p_r}{p_\pi} - 1\right) (\sum_i n_i (v_i - 2) + 2) + 2}{4 + 2\left(\frac{p_r}{p_\pi} - 1\right)} - \frac{2 + \sum_i n_i (v_i - 2)}{6 + 3\left(\frac{p_r}{p_\pi} - 1\right)} - 1$$

$$n_s = \frac{n_i (12 + 6\left(\frac{p_r}{p_\pi} - 1\right)) + \sum_i n_i (v_i - 2) + 3\left(\frac{p_r}{p_\pi} - 1\right) (\sum_i n_i (v_i - 2) + 2) - 10 - 6\left(\frac{p_r}{p_\pi} - 1\right)}{12 + 6\left(\frac{p_r}{p_\pi} - 1\right)}$$

$$n_s = \frac{\sum_i n_i (v_i + 10) + 3\left(\frac{p_r}{p_\pi} - 1\right) \sum_i n_i v_i - 10}{12 + 6\left(\frac{p_r}{p_\pi} - 1\right)} \quad (20)$$

4. Conclusion

In conclusion, the equations presented in this paper as well as other similar formulations, have the potential to be applied in practice for identifying molecular structures from physical samples [15], but they have a major limitation that we believe may be addressed by introducing variables that can be tested in a laboratory such as electrical charges or correction factors [16-17]. Nonetheless, in this article we have established the theoretical foundation of the equations, developed them within the framework of valence bond theory and innovative related concepts [18], and presented them in a clear form that is accessible to readers interested in this area of research [19].

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